

VITAMIN D₃: RESEARCH BREAKTHROUGHS AND THERAPEUTIC USE

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Introduction

Vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol), the natural form of vitamin D, is produced in the skin from 7-dehydrocholesterol. Upon irradiation, 7-dehydrocholesterol produces pre-vitamin D₃ which undergoes a temperature-sensitive rearrangement of three double bonds to form vitamin D₃. The synthesis of vitamin D in the skin is the most important source of vitamin D. Vitamin D can also be taken through nutrition, in the diet, but it is present in only a few food sources, such as little number of fish species, containing relevant levels of vitamin D. Vegetarian diet is limited to the plant vitamin D₂ that is only present in some mushrooms. Commercially dark cultivated white button mushrooms contain low amounts of vitamin D₂, only wild mushrooms or sun-dried mushrooms contain elevated amounts of ergocalciferol [1].

Vitamin D₃ assumes its biological activity by binding with DBP (Vitamin D binding protein), which transports vitamin D and its metabolites from blood serum to the liver. Where vitamin D is hydroxylated at C-25 to produce its major circulating form – 25-hydroxyvitamin [2]. The 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ needs to be further hydroxylated to form 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃. Major sites for conversion of 25(OH)D₃ to 1,25(OH)₂D₃ are kidney and placenta [3].

1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ [1,25(OH)₂D₃] is the hormonally active form of vitamin D. Novel researches show it generates a number of extraskeletal biological responses including inhibition of variety types cancer progression, effects on cardiovascular disorders and mediates a protection against a number of inflammatory, autoimmune and infection diseases [4].

The biological actions of 1,25(OH)₂D₃ are mediated by the VDR. VDR is a polymorphic nuclear receptor and belongs to the steroid receptor family which includes receptors for retinoic acid, thyroid hormone, sex hormones, and adrenal steroids [5]. The heterogeneous loss of function mutations in the VDR caused the 1,25(OH)₂D₃ organ resistance and leads to Hereditary vitamin D-resistant rickets [6]. The genomic mechanism of 1,25(OH)₂D₃ action involves the direct binding of 1,25(OH)₂D₃ activated VDR/RXR to specific DNA sequences [vitamin D response elements (VDREs)] in and around target genes resulting in either activation or repression of transcription [7]. In this way more than 1000 genes are regulated by Vitamin D through the VDR [8]. VDR modulates the expression of genes involved in immune function and cytokine production. The VDR and CYP27B1, the enzyme located in kidneys and target organs, are present in immune competent cells, bronchial and pulmonary epithelial cells, among others,

and is up-regulated following the ligation of specific toll-like receptors by extracellular pathogens, implicating vitamin D in innate immunity [9-14].

By binding the VDR, calcitriol induces several endogenous antimicrobial peptides (AMP) in monocytes, neutrophils and epithelial cells including cathelicidin LL-37, α -defensin, β defensin and neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin and up-regulates nitric oxide (NO) synthase [15-18]. AMPs inhibit infection caused by bacteria, viruses and fungi, while NO synthase augments bacterial killing by up-regulating the oxidative burst in activated macrophages [19-22]. Vitamin D may also induce a Th₂-based response, characterized by high Immunoglobulin IgE and eosinophilia, to combat extracellular infections caused by parasites, protozoa and fungi. In addition to its role in innate immunity, calcitriol suppresses pro-inflammatory cytokines *in vitro* and *in vivo*, and up-regulates anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL10 [23-27]. Since the inflammatory response associated with infections such influenza, pneumonia and sepsis increases both clinical severity and mortality, the ability to reduce inflammation may allow vitamin D to decrease mortality and disease burden in certain infections [28-31].

Notwithstanding the width of possible vitamin D application field, which being known now, large-scale clinical trials are still demanded.

Our review has the aim to summarize current scientific understanding of Vitamin D₃ effects on the immunological field with the focus on its capacity to enhance the anti-infection and anti-inflammatory immune reactivity.

Vitamin D – the innate and adoptive immunity modulator.

In a cross-sectional analysis serum 25(OH)D levels were found to be significantly lower in critically ill septic patients. This was associated with decreased concentrations of the antimicrobial protein cathelicidin [32]. This finding supports the theory that the vitamin D status regulates antimicrobial protein levels of innate immune cells and may be crucial in infection control. Dendritic cells (DC) are also important targets for the immune modulatory effects of vitamin D. Different studies have shown that calcitriol and its analogs can alter function and morphology of DC to induce a more tolerogenic, immature state [33-36]. Immature DC are characterized by decreased levels of MHC class II and co-stimulatory molecule expression (CD40, CD80, CD86), which leads to reduced antigen presentation accompanied by a lower IL12 secretion but an increased production of the tolerogenic interleukin IL10. Calcitriol has also been described to inhibit T cell cytokines such as IL2 and IL17 and toll like receptors on monocytes [37]. High-dose calcitriol supplementation in healthy humans (1 μ g twice daily for 7 days) leads to a significant reduction of the proinflammatory cytokine IL6 produced by peripheral mononuclear cells [38]. It is likely that a combination of these effects results in the induction of potential regulatory T cells which are crucial for controlling immune responses [39]. *In vitro* data are also supported by results from VDR and CYP27B1 knockout

mice which show significantly increased numbers of mature DC and abnormal DC chemotaxis [40].

Early studies of vitamin D effects on human adaptive immune cells demonstrated an expression of the nuclear VDR as well as vitamin D-activating enzymes in both T- and B cells [41]. Actually, VDR expression by these cells is very low in resting conditions but upon activation and proliferation, T- and B cells up-regulate VDR expression significantly, allowing regulation of up to 500 vitamin D responsive genes which influence differentiation and proliferation. In B cells, antiproliferative effects of vitamin D₃ such as inhibition of differentiation, proliferation, initiation of apoptosis and decreased immunoglobulin production were initially considered to be exclusively indirectly mediated by CD4⁺ cells [42]. More recent studies confirmed additional direct effects of vitamin D₃ on B cell function, including inhibition of memory- and plasma-cell generation, as well as promotion of immunoglobulin-producing B cells apoptosis [43]. This control on B cell activation and proliferation may be clinically important in autoimmune diseases as B-cells producing autoreactive antibodies play a major role in the pathophysiology of autoimmunity.

T cells, is also thought to be an important target for the immune modulatory effects of vitamin D different forms. Four potential mechanisms by which vitamin D may influence T cell function have been proposed. There are direct, endocrine effects on T cells mediated via systemic calcitriol; direct, intracrine conversion of 25(OH)D to calcitriol by T cells; direct, paracrine effects of calcitriol on T cells following conversion of 25(OH)D to calcitriol by monocytes or dendritic cells and indirect effects on antigen presentation to T cells mediated via localized APC affected by calcitriol [44]. Vitamin D exposure leads to a shift from a proinflammatory to a more tolerogenic immune status, including very diverse effects on T cell subtypes. Thus, vitamin D₃ suppresses CD4⁺ cell proliferation, differentiation and modulates their cytokine production [45]. In particular, treatment of T cells with calcitriol or analogs inhibits the secretion of proinflammatory Th1 (IL2, IFN- γ , TNF α), Th9 (IL9) and Th22 (IL22) cytokines [46-48], but promotes the production of more anti-inflammatory Th2 cytokines (IL3, IL4, IL5, IL10) [49]. IL17 producing Th17 cells are also affected by vitamin D. Recently, calcitriol was found to directly suppress IL17 production on a transcriptional level and activated human T-cells exposed to calcitriol produced significantly decreased levels of IL17, interferon- γ and IL21 [50, 51]. The same study also revealed a change towards a tolerogenic phenotype, including increased expression of genes typical for regulatory T cells (Tregs), by adding a combination of calcitriol and IL2 to human primary T cell cultures. Tregs act to suppress proinflammatory responses by other immune cells and aim to prevent exaggerated or autoimmune responses [52]. Tregs can be induced and stimulated by vitamin D in an indirect pathway, via APC, including the group of DC which stay in an immature state upon vitamin D treatment and therefore present less antigens. The direct pathway acts via systemic calcitriol effects or intracrine conversion of 25(OH)D to calcitriol

by Tregs themselves. Administration of calcitriol to renal transplant recipients expanded the circulating Treg population [53]. In the subsequent randomized, placebo controlled trial in healthy subjects, the percentage of Tregs in peripheral blood increased significantly after supplementation with high doses of cholecalciferol [54, 55]. Using cholecalciferol supplementation as adjunctive therapy in new onset T1D patients, the percentage of peripheral Tregs increased, although there was no significant difference in Tregs percent between placebo and treatment group after 1 year of supplementation [56].

These results suggest that vitamin D may support the innate and adaptive immune system and could also provide a safe and useful future therapy to support immune tolerance in autoimmune diseases or following transplantation.

Vitamin D₃ supplementation

Though some prospective studies suggest that vitamin D plays a positive role in various infectious processes including tuberculosis, influenza and HIV, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease exacerbations and sepsis [57-59].

The last 10 years of vitamin D application trials are focused on its role in various pulmonary diseases. A majority of these researches studied respiratory tract infections and exacerbations linked to them, pneumonia and tuberculosis.

The placebo, randomized, double blind, single center trial (280 postmenopausal women) that started in 2007 and continued for 3 years shows that supplementation of vitamin D₃ in a daily dose 800 IU for 2 years and 2000 IU for 1 year decreased cold and influenza symptoms and self-reported respiratory tract infections [60].

Another placebo, randomized, double blind, but multicenter trial (430 healthy children) started in 2010 suggested that daily implication of vitD₃ (1,200 IU) for 3 month leads to the decreasing of influenza A incidence and asthma attacks in children with asthma [61]. Majak in not very wide placebo, randomized, double blind, single center research (48 children with new asthma) shows that daily 500 IU of D₃ for 6 month helps to increase lung function, minimize the score of asthma symptoms and number of asthma exacerbations due to respiratory tract infection [62].

Bergman in 2012 in placebo, randomized, double blind, single center trial proposed 4000 IU of D₃ daily for 1 year to 140 participants with an antibody deficiency or participants who have had more than 4 respiratory tract infection episodes during the year. This scheme helps to decrease the rate of infection and number of days on antibiotics by 50 % [63]. Camargo in 2012 successfully used daily D₃ in a dose 300 IU to 247 healthy ~ 10 years-old children for minimizing respiratory tract infection episodes [64]. In patients with moderate to very severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease implication of 100,000 IU of vitamin D₃ with monthly intervals resulted in improvement in lung function, rates of exacerbation, morbidity and mortality, although positive results were limited to participants who were vitamin D deficient at baseline [65]. Cystic fibrosis

patients who received a single 250,000 IU dose of vitamin D₃ while hospitalized experienced a significant increase in hospital-free days during the year and 50,4 % decrease in TNF α concentrations up to 12 weeks [43].

Vitamin D and Tuberculosis

Vitamin D has been widely studied in the prevention and treatment of tuberculosis. Current studies were focused on how calcitriol enhances the antimicrobial effects of macrophages and monocytes – important effector cells, fighting against pathogens such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB). Besides enhancing chemotaxis and phagocytic capabilities of innate immune cells [66], the complex of calcitriol, VDR, and retinoid X receptor directly activates the transcription of antimicrobial peptides such as defensin β 2 (DEFB) and cathelicidin antimicrobial peptide (hCAP18) [67-69]. In detail, monocytes exposed to MTB show a strong induction of the 1 α -hydroxylase CYP27B1 and the vitamin D receptor after recognizing pathogens by toll-like receptors, leading to a direct modulation of gene expression, favoring production of cathelicidin [70]. Besides TLR-signaling, other cytokines such as interferon- γ or IL-4 have been found to also effect CYP27B1 expression [71]. Human cathelicidin (hCAP18) which is cleaved from LL-37 (37-residue active cationic peptide) and then causes destabilization of microbial membranes, is up-regulated in response to infections in humans and also acts against bacteria, viruses and fungi [19].

Several studies tracked the impact of vitamin D on cytokines that promote anti-MTB activity and the resolution of infection. Suppression of antigen-stimulated pro-inflammatory cytokines, attenuation of anti-inflammatory cytokines, and a more rapid treatment-induced resolution of lymphopenia and monocytosis associated with TB infection occurred following 100,000 IU doses of vitamin D₃ given monthly for 4 months [72]. The trial that studied tuberculosis (TB) prevention showed a single dose of 800 IU of vitamin D₃ to cause a significant increase in anthropometric measurements and a 59 % reduction in tuberculin skin test conversion rates when given to children for 6 weeks [73]. Some papers discussed vitamin D both as an adjunct to antibiotic treatment for TB and in its ability to direct killing of MTB [74-76]. Vitamin D implication led to clinical improvements in several studies, including: weight gains (in adults who received two doses of 600,000 IU of vitamin D₃ and children received daily doses of 1000 IU for 8 weeks [76, 77], less tissue involvement was observed after 1,000 IU daily use during 2 months and chest x-ray after 5,000 IU of vitamin D₃ daily for 3 months. Conversely, no improvement on x-ray was seen in children receiving daily doses of vitamin D (1,000 IU over 2 months [77] or adults receiving daily of 10,000 IU for 6 weeks [78] or monthly implication of 50,000 IU given twice doses of vitamin D₃ [79].

Conversion of sputum smear or sputum culture was used to measure response to treatment in several studies, though only sputum culture conversion is independently linked to long-term risk of treatment

failure and relapse [80]. Also it was found [78] that 10,000 IU of vitamin D₃ given daily for 6 weeks to significantly increase sputum smear conversion (100 % in the treatment group vs. 76,7 % in the placebo group, p=0,002).

IFN- γ levels were impacted variably: 2 doses of vitamin D₃ (600,000 IU) led to increasing of IFN- γ expression [76], while a single 100,000 IU dose of vitamin D₂ showed no change [75].

In the result of another trial (95 patients) was no effect on time to sputum culture conversion after adjusting for multiple baseline factors (35 vs 46,5 days, p \leq 0,05), but vitamin D accelerated normalization of erythrocyte sedimentation ratio and serum C-reactive protein in this population. Vitamin D also reduced chemokine production, but it had no effect on IFN- γ [72].

Two studies evaluated vitamin D in combination with another chemical thought to modulate activity against MTB; 5,000 IU of vitamin D₃ given for 4 days alone or in combination with phenylbutyrate induced both circulating levels and transcript expression of the anti-microbial peptide LL-37 [81], while 50,000 IU doses with or without l-arginine (for NO production promotion) showed no significant change in sputum culture conversion rate or x-ray involvement [79].

Negative results in some studies could be explained by variability of the Taq1 vitamin D receptor genotype polymorphism. It was shown that significantly accelerated conversion is appropriate of patients who have a *tt* genotype compared to those with the *Tt* or *TT* genotype.

Thus one study reported a significant benefit of vitamin D evident in 12 subjects with the *tt* Taq1 VDR genotype, with proportions culture positive at week 8 of 0 % and 57 % in the vitamin D and control arms, respectively [75]. There was no benefit of vitamin D in other VDR genotypes. These results were not confirmed by the study, where were founded no effect of VDR genotype on vitamin D in an analysis that included 30 *tt* genotype subjects. In this trial was carried out a subset analysis in 18 patients who were found after enrollment to have multidrug-resistant-tuberculosis. Treatment with second-line drugs began after a mean of 51 days for placebo recipients and 62 days for vitamin D recipients. Six of 10 recipients remained culture positive at week 8 in the placebo arm versus 1 of 8 in the vitamin D arm [75].

As a resume, vitamin D given largely as an adjunctive therapy with traditional anti-tuberculosis regimens in a variety of dose and dosing schedule has some impact on clearance of *M. tuberculosis* from sputum in the wide number randomized controlled multicenter trials of patients with active tuberculosis infection. Patients with infection of MTB with different strains of tuberculosis can take benefits from Vitamin D₃ consumption due to its effect on the clearance of MTB from sputum and on dampening the inflammatory response or anthropometric changes that may help tuberculosis patients recover. A significant microbiologic effect of vitamin D₃ was indicated in several trials that, also, sustained by in vitro tests, where its antimycobacterial effects in cultured macrophages

was shown. Antimycobacterial effect is provided enhances the expression of the anti-microbial peptide human cathelicidin (hCAP18) in cultured macrophages [82]. The clinical benefit after high vitamin D₃ doses administrating to patients does not depend of their vitamin D₃ marked deficiency. The cause of this variation remains unexplained. The Role of genetic polymorphisms in the vitamin D receptor, or in the multiple enzymes involved in its metabolism in vitD₃ effectiveness remains unproved. Measurement of calcitriol-induced antimycobacterial activity in ex vivo whole blood culture in future studies may help in understanding the functional effects of specific genetic polymorphisms. So, big attention will be required in future studies to determine mechanism of vitamin effect on patients with tuberculosis.

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VITAMIN D₃: RESEARCH BREAKTHROUGHS AND THERAPEUTIC USE

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Vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol), the natural form of vitamin D, is produced in the skin from 7-dehydrocholesterol. The synthesis of vitamin D in the skin is the most important source of vitamin D. Vitamin D can also be taken through nutrition, in the diet, but it is present in only a few food sources, containing relevant levels of vitamin D. 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ [1,25(OH)₂D₃] is the hormonally active form of vitamin D. Novel researches show it generates a number of extraskelatal biological responses including inhibition of variety types cancer progression, effects on cardiovascular disorders and mediates a protection against a number of inflammatory, autoimmune and infection diseases The biological actions of 1,25(OH)₂D₃ are mediated by the VDR. The genomic mechanism of 1,25(OH)₂D₃ action involves the direct binding of 1,25(OH)₂D₃ activated VDR/RXR to specific DNA sequences in and around target genes resulting in either activation or repression of transcription [7] VDR modulates the expression of genes involved in immune function and cytokine production. The VDR and CYP27B1, the enzyme located in kidneys and target organs, are present in immune competent cells, bronchial and pulmonary epithelial cells, among others, and is up-regulated following the ligation of specific toll-like receptors by extracellular pathogens, implicating vitamin D in innate immunity. By binding the VDR, calcitriol induces several endogenous antimicrobial peptides (AMP) in monocytes, neutrophils and epithelial cells including cathelicidin LL-37, α -defensin, β defensin and neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin and up-regulates nitric oxide (NO) synthase. Since the inflammatory response associated with infections such influenza, pneumonia and sepsis increases both clinical severity and mortality, the ability to reduce inflammation may allow vitamin D to decrease mortality and disease burden in certain infections. Notwithstanding the width of possible vitamin D application field, which being known now, large-scale clinical trials are still demanded. Our review has the aim to summarize current scientific understanding of Vitamin D₃ effects on the immunological field with the focus on its capacity to enhance the anti-infection and anti-inflammatory immune reactivity. **Vitamin D and Tuberculosis.** Vitamin D has been widely studied in the prevention and treatment of tuberculosis. Current studies were focused on how calcitriol enhances the antimicrobial effects of macrophages and monocytes –

important effector cells, fighting against pathogens such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MBT). Several studies tracked the impact of vitamin D on cytokines that promote anti-MTB activity and the resolution of infection. Suppression of antigen-stimulated pro-inflammatory cytokines, attenuation of anti-inflammatory cytokines, and a more rapid treatment-induced resolution of lymphopenia and monocytosis associated with TB infection occurred following 100,000 IU doses of vitamin D₃ given monthly for 4 months. Conversion of sputum smear or sputum culture was used to measure response to treatment in several studies, though only sputum culture conversion is independently linked to long-term risk of treatment failure and relapse. Also it was found that 10,000 IU of vitamin D₃ given daily for 6 weeks to significantly increase sputum smear conversion (100 % in the treatment group vs. 76,7 % in the placebo group, p=0,002). IFN- γ levels were impacted variably: 2 doses of vitamin D₃ (600,000 IU) led to increasing of IFN- γ expression, while a single 100,000 IU dose of vitamin D₂ showed no change. Negative results in some studies could be explained by variability of the Taq1 vitamin D receptor genotype polymorphism. It was shown that significantly accelerated conversion is appropriate of patients who have a *tt* genotype compared to those with the *Tt* or *TT* genotype. But these results were not confirmed by another study, where were founded no interaction between VDR genotype effectiveness of vitamin D. Several trials show vitamin D given largely as an adjunctive therapy with traditional anti-tuberculosis regimens in a variety of dose and dosing schedule has some impact on clearance of MBT from sputum in the wide number randomized controlled multicenter trials of patients with active tuberculosis infection. Patients with infection of MBT with different strains of tuberculosis can take benefits from Vitamin D₃ consumption due to its effect on the clearance of MTB from sputum and on dampening the inflammatory response or anthropometric changes that may help tuberculosis patients recover. A significant microbiologic effect of vitamin D₃ was indicated in several trials that, also, sustained by in vitro tests, where its antimycobacterial effects in cultured macrophages was shown. Antimycobacterial effect is provided enhances the expression of the anti-microbial peptide human cathelicidin (hCAP18) in cultured macrophages. The clinical benefit after high vitamin D₃ doses administrating to patients does not depend of their vitamin D₃ marked deficiency. The cause of this variation remains unexplained. The role of genetic polymorphisms in the vitamin D receptor, or in the multiple enzymes involved in its metabolism in vitD₃ effectiveness remains unproved. Measurement of calcitriol-induced antimycobacterial activity in ex vivo whole blood culture in future studies may help in understanding the functional effects of specific genetic polymorphisms. So, big attention will be required in future studies to determine mechanism of vitamin effect on patients with tuberculosis.

Keywords: Vitamin D₃, cholecalciferol, VDR, infection, pulmonary disease, tuberculosis, innate immunity, adoptive immunity, antimicrobial effect